
TO ANALYZE THE IMPACT OF UNIFIED PAYMENT INTERFACE AND SECURITY MEASURES AMONG YOUNGSTERS**Mr. Devesh Kailas Satre**

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ABSTRACT

Digital payment platforms have become a regular part of our daily life, and I've noticed UPI is especially common among young people in India. In this research, I set out to understand not just how we use UPI, but also how convenient we find it and whether we actually trust the system. This study takes a closer look at how young people are using UPI how often they use it, how convenient they find it by combining surveys and interviews, the research explores what young users know about UPI's security, how they feel about it, and how they behave when using these safety measures. UPI and their overall confidence in going cashless. Finally, the study suggests ways to improve both security and the user experience, aiming to encourage safer financial habits and help more people join the digital economy. My aim here is to share practical ideas on improving both security and user-friendliness, helping more young people take part in the digital economy safely.

Keywords: UPI, digital payments, youth adoption, security measures, payment behaviour, fintech

I. INTRODUCTION

Unified Payments Interface (UPI) has transformed the way digital transactions are carried out in India by offering a fast, simple, and widely accessible payment system. With the increasing use of smartphones and internet connectivity, UPI has become one of the most preferred methods for transferring money and making everyday payments. It allows users to send and receive money instantly using mobile-based applications without the need for cash or physical cards. Over the years, the usage of UPI has increased rapidly, especially among young users, due to its convenience, speed, and wide acceptance across merchants and service providers. From small retail stores to large online platforms, UPI has become a common mode of transaction. This strong growth highlights the importance of understanding how users perceive UPI in terms of usability, trust, and security. Therefore, this study focuses on analyzing the impact of UPI usage and its related security measures among youngsters.

A. Research Problem

While UPI has simplified payment processes and enhanced financial inclusion, its rapid adoption has also introduced new challenges, particularly in the realm of cybersecurity. The LocalCircles [2] survey revealed that one in five Indian families using UPI has fallen victim to digital payment fraud at least once since 2022. This creates a paradox where the very convenience that drives adoption also becomes a source of vulnerability, especially among youngsters who are often the earliest adopters of new technology.

B. Research Objectives**This study aims to:**

1. To analyse the adoption patterns and usage behaviour of UPI among youngsters
2. To Examine the security perceptions and concerns of young UPI users
3. To Investigate the impact of security measures on user confidence and adoption
4. To identify key factors influencing youth engagement with UPI systems
5. To provide recommendations for enhancing security awareness and measures.

II. UPI ADOPTION AND GROWTH TRENDS

A 2024 analysis by ACI Worldwide [1] estimates that India processed nearly half of all real-time payment transactions worldwide in 2023 (ACI Worldwide [1], 2024). Young Indians, benefiting from widespread smartphone ownership and digital literacy, have driven much of this expansion. In a 2024 ISRDO [5] study, more than four-fifths of surveyed youths cited transaction speed and simplicity as their chief motivations for choosing digital payments over cash (ISRDO [5], 2024). The relevance of mobile apps such as Paytm, Google Pay, and PhonePe [4] has further lowered barriers to entry, accelerating UPI's uptake among tech-savvy users.

III. SECURITY CHALLENGES AND MEASURES

Security plays a very important role in the success of any digital payment system, and UPI is no exception. Since UPI involves direct access to bank accounts, users expect a high level of protection against fraud and unauthorized transactions. To ensure this, UPI uses multiple layers of safety checks during every transaction process. Each transaction requires user verification before completion, which helps in preventing misuse. In addition, UPI platforms regularly update their systems to detect suspicious activities and block fraudulent attempts. Despite these measures, users still face risks such as phishing, fake payment requests, and social engineering attacks. Therefore, improving user awareness along with strong technical protection remains essential for maintaining trust in UPI.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of existing statistical data with primary research through a structured questionnaire. The research design is descriptive and analytical, aimed at understanding both the current state of UPI adoption among youngsters and the underlying factors influencing their behaviour and security perceptions.

B. Data Collection Instrument

The primary data collection instrument is a comprehensive Google Form questionnaire designed to capture multiple dimensions of UPI usage among youngsters. The questionnaire is structured into five main categories:

Usage Frequency and Patterns: Examining how often youngsters use UPI, their preferred apps, device preferences, and recommendation behaviour.

Understanding and Awareness: Assessing users' comprehension of UPI features, awareness of security risks, and interest in learning about safe usage practices.

Security Perceptions: Investigating users' beliefs about UPI safety, primary concerns, difficulties encountered, and experiences with failed transactions.

User Experience: Exploring user satisfaction, comfort levels, preferred reasons for usage, and comparative assessments with other payment methods.

Future Outlook: Gauging expectations about UPI's future role and accessibility for different age groups.

C. Target Population

The target demographic consists of youngsters, broadly defined as individuals aged 15-30, who represent the primary users of UPI systems

D. Data Analysis Framework

The analysis incorporates both primary survey data (184 Respondents) and secondary statistical information from authoritative sources including NPCI, RBI, and peer-reviewed research publications. Statistical analysis techniques include descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and comparative assessment of user behaviour patterns.

V. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

184 responses

Fig. 1. Frequency of UPI usage among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 1, 60.3% respondents use UPI on a daily basis, followed by 27.2% who use it weekly, 8.2% monthly users, and only 4.3% who rarely or never use UPI.

184 responses

Fig. 2. Level of understanding of UPI features among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 2, 43.5% respondents reported a good level of understanding of UPI features, 33.2% rated their understanding as excellent, 17.4% as average, while only 6% indicated poor understanding.

184 responses

Fig. 3. Perception of UPI safety compared to cash among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 3, 85.3% respondents believe that using UPI is safer than cash, while 14.7% feel that cash is safer.

184 responses

Fig. 4. Primary reasons for using UPI among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 4, convenience is the primary reason for using UPI for 48.9% of respondents, followed by faster transactions for 26.6%, rewards or cashback for 17.9%, and peer pressure for a 6.5% of users.

184 responses

Fig. 5. Awareness of potential security risks while using UPI among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 5, 79.3% of respondents are aware of the potential security risks associated with using UPI, while 20.7% reported that they are not aware of such risks.

184 responses

Fig. 6. Difficulties faced by users while using UPI.

As shown in Fig. 6, 47.3% of respondents reported that they do not face any difficulty and find UPI easy to use, while 23.9% found the user interface difficult to navigate, 17.4% cited security concerns, and 11.4% reported lack of support as the main difficulty.

184 responses

Fig. 7. Interest of respondents in learning more about safe and effective use of UPI.

As shown in Fig. 7, 69% of respondents expressed interest in learning more about using UPI safely and effectively, whereas 31% indicated that they are not.

184 responses

Fig. 8. Primary concerns while using UPI among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 8, 41.8% of respondents identified security risks (risk of fraud) as their primary concern, followed by privacy or data misuse for 27.2%, transaction failures for 24.5%, while only 6.5% reported having no major concerns.

184 responses

Fig. 9. Sources through which respondents first learned about UPI.

As shown in Fig. 9, 46.2% of respondents first learned about UPI through friends or family, followed by social media for 33.7%, banks or financial institutions for 15.2%, and news or advertisements for 4.9%.

184 responses

Fig. 10. Comparison of UPI transaction speed with other payment methods.

As shown in Fig. 10, 76.6% of respondents believe that UPI is faster than other payment methods such as cards or net banking, whereas 23.4% do not share this opinion.

184 responses

Fig. 11. Comfort level of respondents while using UPI.

As shown in Fig. 11, 44.0% of respondents reported being very comfortable while using UPI, 33.7% were somewhat comfortable, 15.8% were neutral, and only 6.5% felt uncomfortable using UPI.

184 responses

Fig. 12. Devices used by respondents for UPI transactions.

As shown in Fig. 12, 91.8% of respondents use smartphones for UPI transactions, followed by tablets (4.3%), computers (3.3%), and other devices (0.5%).

184 responses

Fig. 13. Most frequently used UPI applications among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 13, Google Pay is the most frequently used UPI application among 40.8% of respondents, followed by PhonePe at 27.2%, Paytm at 18.5%, and BHIM UPI at 13.6%.

184 responses

Fig. 14. Willingness of respondents to recommend UPI to others.

As shown in Fig. 14, 78.8% of respondents have recommended UPI to others, whereas 21.2% have not recommended it.

184 responses

Fig. 15. Key advantages of UPI as perceived by respondents.

As shown in Fig. 15, speed of transactions is the most valued advantage of UPI for 41.3% of respondents, followed by ease of use (25.0%), wide acceptance (22.8%), and lower transaction costs (10.9%).

184 responses

Fig. 16. Level of trust in UPI compared to other payment methods among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 16, 83.7% of respondents trust UPI more than other payment methods, whereas 16.3% indicated that they do not trust UPI more than other methods.

184 responses

Fig. 17. Experience of unresolved failed UPI transactions among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 17, 33.2% of respondents reported experiencing a failed UPI transaction that was not resolved quickly, while 66.8% indicated that they had not faced such an issue.

184 responses

Fig. 18. Respondents' perception of UPI as the future dominant payment method.

As shown in Fig. 18, 88% of respondents believe that UPI will become the most common form of payment in the future, while 12% do not share this belief.

184 responses

Fig. 19. Overall satisfaction of respondents with UPI services.

As shown in Fig. 19, 76.1% of respondents expressed overall satisfaction with UPI services, while 23.9% reported that they are not satisfied.

184 responses

Fig. 20. Ease of resolving issues related to UPI transactions among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 20, 35.3% of respondents found it very easy to resolve issues related to UPI transactions, 39.1% found it somewhat easy, 17.4% found it difficult, and 8.2% reported that it is very difficult.

184 responses

Fig. 21. Importance of rewards or cashback in motivating UPI usage among respondents.

As shown in Fig. 21, 44.0% of respondents consider rewards or cashback to be very important while using UPI, 27.7% consider them somewhat important, 16.8% find them not important, and 11.4% stated that they do not care about such rewards.

184 responses

Fig. 22. Preference of respondents for using UPI over other digital payment methods.

As shown in Fig. 22, 81.5% of respondents prefer using UPI over other digital payment methods such as wallets or cards, while 18.5% do not prefer UPI over other methods.

184 responses

Fig. 23. Respondents who do not prefer using UPI over other payment methods.

As shown in Fig. 23, 70.1% of respondents indicated that they do not prefer using UPI over other payment methods, while 29.9% reported that they still prefer using UPI.

VI. DISCUSSION

The Paradox of Convenience and Security

The findings reveal a fundamental paradox in UPI adoption among youngsters: the same convenience features that drive widespread adoption also create potential security vulnerabilities. Young users are attracted to UPI's simplicity and speed, but this ease of use can lead to complacency regarding security practices.

VII. LIMITATIONS

A. Study Limitations

The geographic scope of available data varies across sources, and some findings may not be representative of all regions or demographic subgroups within the youth population.

VIII. FUTURE RESEARCH

Comparative Analysis: Perform comparative studies examining UPI adoption and security experiences across different countries and digital payment systems.

Behavioural Economics Research: Investigate the psychological and behavioural factors that influence young users' security practices and risk-taking behaviors in digital payments.

IX. CONCLUSION

The research indicates that while young users have accepted UPI with their open hands UPI's convenience and features, their awareness of digital security has not grown at the same pace. Although most of capable youth can operate UPI, around few people have reported experiencing some form of fraud. This gap highlights the urgent need for stronger security measures and awareness campaigns. The study finds that UPI's future growth among young users will depend on addressing what can be called the convenience and security paradox. Users require protection of their bank accounts. Seeing the right balance for collaboration between technology providers and regulators. By combining innovative technical aspects with effective security education for the users, it is possible to strengthen confidence in digital transactions.

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